

BIOPOLE Newsletter

Spring 2024

compiled by Ruta Hamilton (BAS)

Welcome to our seasonal newsletter!

BIOPOLE is at an interesting juncture between reflecting on its progress so far and planning for the next set of major fieldwork operations. As was evident at our recent Annual Science Meeting, observational work at both poles has been highly successful and there are now large quantities of samples awaiting further laboratory analyses. These analyses not only provide new information on understudied environmental processes, but are key datasets with which to parameterise and validate models. Models are essential to simulate environmental processes and determine how they may respond to change. Furthermore, BIOPOLE uses these models to instruct future field operations so that sampling is focussed on areas and processes of greatest uncertainty. This integration of observation and modelling is a particular strength of BIOPOLE, and essential to addressing how carbon and nutrients flow through polar marine ecosystems and affect Earth system processes.

It was understood from the start of BIOPOLE that we cannot take on such a major challenge alone, and networking with the wider international science community has been a major priority. This present newsletter includes a number of examples of how BIOPOLE is linking and coordinating internationally. Read on to learn more about the joint workshop with the Australian Centre for Excellence in Antarctic studies, the dedicated BIOPOLE session at the Arctic Science Week, and presentations at the UN Decade of the Oceans conference, the 7th Zooplankton Science symposium, and the Netherlands Polar Day.

As much as BIOPOLE has achieved a great deal of outreach with regards its field operations, modelling has received much less attention even though it accounts for around half of our science objectives. BIOPOLE is therefore providing a platform to highlight the incredible work done by our modellers. Read the profile of one of BIOPOLE's senior modellers and work package 3 co-lead, Adrian Martin, to find out more about what makes this particular modeller tick. Also, learn more about our wonderful new lead of the BIOPOLE Early Career Researcher network, Laura Taylor.

Geraint Tarling (Principal Investigator)

Equality, Diversity and Inclusion (EDI)

Application for the 2024 BAS EDI Internship Programme is now open. We encourage you to share this with those who may be interested. BIOPOLE project member, [Clara Manno](#), is willing to share her experiences of successful applications.

[More information and how to apply](#)

The screenshot shows the British Antarctic Survey website. The header includes the logo and navigation links: About, Science, Data, Polar operations, People, News and media, Jobs at BAS, and Contact BAS. The main content area features a large image of a diverse group of people, with the text "EDI Internship Programme" overlaid. Below the image, there is a paragraph of text describing the organization's commitment to diversity and inclusion. To the right of the text are social media sharing icons for Facebook, LinkedIn, and X, and a "Featured" label. At the bottom of the page, the text "British Antarctic Survey 2024 Equality, Diversity and Inclusion Internship Programme" is displayed.

British Antarctic Survey
NATURAL ENVIRONMENT RESEARCH COUNCIL

About - Science - Data - Polar operations - People - News and media - Jobs at BAS - Contact BAS

EDI Internship Programme

The British Antarctic Survey (part of UK Research and Innovation – UKRI), is a world-leading centre for polar science and polar operations, addressing issues of global importance and helping society adapt to a changing world. Our aim is to embrace diversity in all its forms and provide staff with a sense of belonging no matter their characteristics, culture, experience, education or economic background. We employ colleagues from across the globe, each contributing to our ethos of excellence.

Share this

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Featured

British Antarctic Survey 2024 Equality, Diversity and Inclusion Internship Programme

Written by [Nadine Johnston](#), [Huw Griffiths](#), and [Clara Manno](#)

ECR Updates

The BIOPOLE mentoring scheme is now well underway with three mentor/mentee pairs meeting regularly to help the ECRs work towards a range of different goals. The mentoring scheme is available for ECRs to sign up to at any point (just fill in this short [form](#)). If anyone is interested in being a mentor to a BIOPOLE ECR who isn't already on the list, please let us know!

While the ECRs haven't been on any exciting fieldwork in the last couple of months, Arctic field season planning is well underway for Alanna Grant among other ECRs involved, and planning is beginning for ECRs involved with Antarctic fieldwork later in the year.

Written by [Laura Taylor](#)

BIOPOLE Annual Science Meeting 2024

The 2nd BIOPOLE Annual Science Meeting took place from the 6th to the 8th of March 2024 at the [British Antarctic Survey](#) in Cambridge and online. BIOPOLE [Project Members](#), [Early Career Researchers](#) (ECRs), Members of the [Programme Advisory Board](#) (PAB), [Science](#) and [Strategic Partners](#) were invited to participate. Around 50 in-person and 13 virtual participants attended the hybrid BIOPOLE Annual Science Meeting.

[Read more on BIOPOLE website](#)

Written by [Ruta Hamilton](#)

Joint BIOPOLE-ACEAS Workshop

BIOPOLE Science Partner, Philip Boyd (Australian Centre for Excellence in Antarctic Studies, ACEAS, and the Institute for Antarctic Marine Studies, IMAS), and BIOPOLE Project Members, Nadine Johnston and Geraint Tarling, co-convened a two-day workshop *'East meets West – A joint BIOPOLE-ACEAS Workshop to strengthen international circumpolar collaborations'* 14-15 March 2024 at the Institute for Antarctic Marine Studies, IMAS, and the Commonwealth Scientific and Industrial Research Organisation (CSIRO), Hobart, Tasmania, Australia.

The workshop was kindly hosted by Philip and held under the auspices of the BIOPOLE East-West Antarctic Forum, which fosters greater international collaboration across the Southern Ocean with partners, institutes, and initiatives with similar research objectives.

[Read more on BIOPOLE website](#)

Written by Nadine Johnston, Geraint Tarling and Aidan Hunter

BIOPOLE at the 7th Zooplankton Production Symposium

[Aidan Hunter](#), [Nadine Johnston](#), [Dan Mayor](#), [Kathryn Cook](#) and [Geraint Tarling](#) attended the [7th ICES/PICES Zooplankton Production Symposium](#) in Hobart, Tasmania (17-21 March 2024). The conference was packed with sessions of direct relevance to BIOPOLE research, particularly on understanding the ecology of calanoid copepods and the contribution of zooplankton to the biological carbon pump.

[Read more on BIOPOLE website](#)

Written by [Geraint Tarling](#)

BIOPOLE Session at the Arctic Science Summit Week 2024

[Alanna Grant](#), ECR, from [UK Centre for Ecology & Hydrology](#) hosted a BIOPOLE special session at the [Arctic Science Summit Week](#) in Edinburgh in March 2024. The session focused on the work completed by [WP1](#) in [Ny-Ålesund, Svalbard, in July 2023](#). Presentations were given by [Bryan Spears](#), [Alanna Grant](#), [Amy Pickard](#), [Kate Hendry](#), [Justyna Olszewska](#), and [Isabelle Fournier](#) and the session was chaired by [Rebecca McKenzie](#). Interpreted results were presented from analysis of greenhouse gases, metals, algae process experiments, and physical and bio-optical properties of Kongsfjorden. River discharge was highlighted as a crucial knowledge gap, and ideas were discussed as to how this could be solved in the future. The session attracted a multi-national audience and provided a great opportunity to share our results with the wider arctic research community and foster new networking and collaboration opportunities.

[Read more on BIOPOLE website](#)

Written by [Alanna Grant](#)

Flying the Polar Flag at the UN Ocean Decade Conference 2024

Amongst 1500 other delegates from around the world, [Jen Freer](#) (BIOPOLE Project Member, BAS), [Amy Swiggs](#) (BIOPOLE Project Member, CPOM) and [Nadine Johnston](#) (BIOPOLE Project Member, BAS), were lucky enough to be selected to attend and present at the first [UN Ocean Decade Conference](#) held in April 2024 in sunny Barcelona. The vision of the UN Ocean Decade is to generate “the science we need for the ocean we want”. The aims of this conference were to bring the global Ocean Decade community together, to celebrate and take stock of progress, and set joint priorities for the future. As an official [Decade Action](#), we were there to showcase BIOPOLE’s research efforts and highlight how our science aligns with many of the Decade’s priorities and recommendations.

[Read more on BIOPOLE website](#)

Written by [Jen Freer](#), [Amy Swiggs](#) and [Nadine Johnston](#)

Feature on Laura Taylor

I'm [Laura Taylor](#), a PhD student at [BAS](#) working on Southern Ocean biogeochemistry. My work involves exploring the interactions between the carbon and silica cycles across Southern Ocean environments, particularly in relation to different sources of nutrient input to the ocean from ice. Before starting my PhD and joining BIOPOLE, I completed my undergraduate and masters degrees at [UEA](#).

[Read more on BIOPOLE website](#)

Feature on Adrian Martin

I am [Dr Adrian Martin](#) and I'm based in the Marine Systems Modelling group at [National Oceanography Centre \(NOC\)](#).

Like many in oceanography I have been environmentally recycled from another field. One of the great things about marine science is that it attracts so many different backgrounds. My background is more in physics and I benefitted from the open-mindedness of marine scientists who gave me a chance to apply my numerical skills to ocean ecology problems after my PhD and I've been at NOC ever since – longer than I choose to remember.

Despite being originally being employed as a modeller and sitting in a modelling group, oceanography encourages multidisciplinary and I was on my first cruise within the first year at NOC and have even been chief scientist on a cruise a couple of times now.

[Read more on BIOPOLE website](#)

BIOPOLE at the Netherlands Polar Day

[Kate Hendry](#) attended the [Netherlands Polar Day](#) on April 23rd in the Museon-Omniversum in The Hague. The NL Polar Day, arranged by the Dutch Research Council (NWO)'s [Netherlands Polar Programme](#) team, the [Ministry of Foreign Affairs](#) and the [Association of Polar Early Career Scientists \(APECS\)](#), every year brings together researchers from around the Netherlands from universities, research institutes, tourism and industry who are interested in all things Arctic and Antarctic. The Netherlands have a strong history of polar research, and rely on international collaborations for infrastructure access: in the Arctic this is largely through their links with the [Alfred Wegener Institute \(AWI\)](#) in Germany, and in the Antarctic through their Memorandum of Understanding with [BAS](#). For example, [Rothera](#) hosts the Dirk Gerritz lab, which was built in 2012.

[Read more on BIOPOLE website](#)

Kate Hendry at the NL Polar Day 2024 by Tom Doms

Written by [Kate Hendry](#)

Exploring the Relationship between Sea Ice and Phytoplankton Growth in the Weddell Gyre Using Satellite and Argo Float Data

BIOPOLE is drawing excellent PhD students to work on complementary topics. Here is a great recent example, summarised by lead author [Clara Douglas](#) and co-author, [Pete Brown](#).

In this study, we assessed the impact of sea ice in driving variability in biological activity within the Weddell Gyre using data from both satellites and Biogeochemical-Argo floats. Situated within the sea ice zone, the region is comprised of a relatively small shelf area (water depths shallower than 2000m) and an expansive area of open ocean.

Although the highest daily rates of net primary production (NPP) are consistently

observed in the continental shelf region, the open-ocean region's larger size and much longer ice-free season mean that it dominates biological carbon uptake within the Weddell Gyre over the course of a year.

Our research revealed that the area of ice-free water in the summer plays a pivotal role in determining the total annual NPP within the region. A larger ice-free area results in increased annual NPP, suggesting a regime predominantly limited by the restriction of light through sea ice to the surface ocean.

However a drop-off does occur - areas that are ice free for longer than 130 days appear to become limited, with both satellite NPP and float chlorophyll-a and particulate organic carbon data showing that a decline in NPP occurs before the end of the ice-free season.

Float data suggest that there are changes in phytoplankton dynamics through the season, potentially as a response to nutrient limitation or grazing pressures. These results indicate that in a warmer and more ice-free Weddell Gyre, notwithstanding compensating changes in nutrient supply, NPP is likely to be enhanced only up to a certain limit of ice-free days.

Understanding the drivers of inter-annual and seasonal variability in phytoplankton activity within off-shore areas is crucial, given its significance for both current and future ecosystem functioning amid changing sea ice dynamics in warming oceans.

[Read the full research article](#)

(a) Percent cumulative chlorophyll-a at the surface (0–20 m) and between 0–200 m for all completed annual cycles by the floats between 2015–2021. (b) Box and whisker plots indicating the range in the number of days from ice melt to (i) sea ice return, (ii) low solar angle (loss of satellite observations), (iii) surface bloom end and (iv) depth-integrated bloom end. The orange line represents the median value for each dataset, the box represents the first and third quartiles, and the whiskers extend to 1.5 times the inter-quartile range.

Written by [Clara Douglas](#) and [Pete Brown](#)

Upcoming Relevant Events

Goldschmidt2024

18-23 August 2024, Chicago, USA

For more information about the conference and to register, [please click here](#)

XI SCAR Open Science Conference

19-23 August 2024, Pucón, Chile

For more information about the conference and to register, [please click here](#)

Challenger Society Conference

2-6 September 2024, Oban, Scotland

[Note: PICCOLO project members are attending]

For more information about the conference and to register, [please click here](#)

2024 European Polar Science Week

3-6 September 2024, Copenhagen, Denmark

[Note: Jen Freer has submitted a session proposal on copepod diapause]

For more information about the conference and to register, [please click here](#)

